

Advanced Techniques in Breast Cancer Prediction: A Comprehensive Approach

Darksha Khanum (Stream: M.Sc. (CS), Semester: 4, University Roll No: 15299022001,
Paper Code: MCS491, Paper Name: Dissertation DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11383981

30th May,2024

ABSTRACT:

Breast cancer remains a significant global health concern, demanding early detection and accurate prediction methods to improve patient outcomes. Machine learning (ML) algorithms have emerged as powerful tools in the domain of medical diagnostics, offering the potential to enhance breast cancer prediction through the analysis of diverse patient data. In this study, we applied five machine learning algorithms: Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision tree, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Naïve Bayes Classifier on the Breast Cancer dataset, after obtaining the results, a performance evaluation and comparison is carried out between these different classifiers. The main objective of this research paper is to predict and diagnosis breast cancer, using machine learning algorithms, and find out the most effective with respect to the confusion matrix, accuracy, and precision. It is observed that Random Forest outperformed all other classifiers and achieved the highest accuracy (90.0%). All the work done is based on python programming language and Scikit-learn library.

Keywords: *Breast cancer;Prediction;Random Forest; Logistic Regression; KNN; Naïve Bayes; Accuracy; Precision*

1. INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer is one of the most prevalent cancers affecting women worldwide, emphasizing the critical need for accurate and timely diagnostic tools. Early detection significantly improves patient outcomes by enabling prompt interventions and tailored strategies. Traditional diagnostic methods, while valuable, often exhibit limitations in sensitivity and specificity. In recent years, the integration of machine learning (ML) algorithms in healthcare has gathered considerable attention for its potential to address these challenges. ML techniques can analyze vast amounts of patient data, demographic information, clinical variables, and imaging data, to identify intricate patterns associated with breast cancer. This introduction provides an overview of the role of ML algorithms in breast cancer prediction, discussing their significance, methodologies, challenges, and implications for improving patient care. By leveraging ML algorithms, clinicians can enhance diagnostic accuracy, optimize treatment planning, and ultimately contribute to better outcomes for patients affected by breast cancer. This paper mainly gives a comparison between the performance of five classifiers: Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Naïve Bayes which according to research community are among the most influential data mining algorithms and among the top 10 data mining algorithms. Our objective is to predict and diagnose breast cancer, using machine learning algorithms, and find out the most effective based on the performance of each classifier in terms of confusion matrix, accuracy, precision, and sensitivity.

2. METHODOLOGY

The main objective of our experiment is to identify the effective and predictive algorithm for detection of breast cancer; therefore, we applied machine learning classifiers Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree, K-

Nearest Neighbors (KNN) on BreastCancer dataset and evaluate the results obtained to define which model provides a higher accuracy.

Fig. 1: Process Flow Diagram

Our methodology begins with data acquisition followed by pre-processing, which contain four steps viz: data cleaning, select attributes, set target role and features extraction. The prepared data is used to build machine learning algorithms that can predict breast cancer for a new set of measurements. To evaluate the algorithm performances, we show the model new data for which we have labels. This is usually done by splitting the labeled data we have collected into two

parts.i.e. Train_Test_split_method. 80% of the data is used to build our machine learning model, which is called the training data or training set. 20% of the data will be used to assess how well the model works and is called the test data or test set. After testing the models, we compared the obtained result to select the algorithm that provides the high accuracy and identify the most predictive algorithm for the detection of breast cancer.

2.1 Experiment Environment

All the experiments on the machine learning algorithms described during this paper were conducted using Scikit-learn library and Python Programming language. Scikit-learn is a free software machine learning library for the Python Programming language. It features various classification, regression and clustering algorithms including random forests, logistic regression, decision tree, naïve bayes and KNN, and is designed to interoperate with the Python numerical and scientific libraries like NumPy, Matplotlib, Pandas and Seaborn.

2.2 Dataset Acquisition

In our study, we use Breast Cancer Diagnostic dataset from Kaggle. The feature of dataset is computed from a digitized image of breast cancer sample obtained from fine-needle aspirate (FNA). The characteristics of the cell nuclei present in the images are determined from these features. Breast Cancer Diagnostic has 569 instances (Benign:357, Malignant:212), 2 classes (62.74% Benign(0) and 37.26% Malignant(1), and 12 integer-valued attributes (-Id -Diagnosis -Radius -Texture -Perimeter -Area -Smoothness -Compactness -Concavity -Concave points -Symmetry -Fractal dimension).

Fig. 2: BREAST CANCER DIAGNOSTIC DATASETS

2.3 Data Visualization

Data Visualization is a key aspect of ML. It helps one to comprehend and convey the data to another person in a meaningful way. Matplotlib and Seaborn are some of the several python data visualization libraries. It is essential in analyzing large amounts of information and to make decisions. It employs the use of pictorial elements such as maps, plots, patterns, graph trends, etc. to provide the user with an easy method of comprehending the data.

For better visualization of the data, we used the seaborn library which is a powerful tool for visualizing pairwise relationships in a dataset. It creates a grid of axes such that each variable in the Data Frame is shared across the y-axes, and each variable is plotted against every other variable. Additionally, it provides the ability to differentiate between categories using the

'hue' parameter, making it particularly useful for exploratory data analysis as shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3: Visualizing Data with Pair plots

In the next step features are selected using correlations, recursive feature elimination with cross-validation is performed, and attribute categorization is performed. Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, KNN and Naïve Bayes classification are used to train the model and predict. As shown in Fig. 4, to gain insights into the relationships between variables in our dataset, we employ a heatmap visualization of correlation. This visualization technique provides a clear and intuitive representation of how each variable correlates with others.

Fig. 4: Numerical Correlation of Variables

As part of this work, we use the normalization technique for feature scaling to convert feature values into mean-centered distribution with unit standard deviation, and this feature scaling method has been widely used in Machine Learning algorithms.

2.4 Machine Learning Algorithms

In our project, the predictive analysis of the machine learning algorithms is achieved. The machine learning algorithms applied in our project are:

2.4.1 Random Forest Classifier

I. The Function

The Random Forest classifier is an ensemble learning method that constructs multiple decision trees during training and outputs the mode of the classes (classification) or the mean prediction (regression) of the individual trees. Each tree is trained on a random subset of the training data, and predictions are made by averaging the results from all trees (for regression) or taking a majority vote (for classification). The algorithm introduces randomness both in the selection of the data points and the features used for splitting, resulting in improved generalization performance. The equation for the random forest prediction is:

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N T_i(x)$$

Where $\hat{y}$ is the predicted output, N is the number of trees, and $T_i(x)$ is the prediction of the i th tree for input x .

II. Implementation

The Random Forest Classifier is implemented as below:

```

from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
# Initialize and train the model

clf_rf = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=42)
clf_rf.fit(X_train, Y_train)

# Evaluate the model
y_pred = clf_rf.predict(X_test)
ac = accuracy_score(Y_test, y_pred)
print('Accuracy is: ', ac * 100)

# Generate confusion matrix and plot it
cm = confusion_matrix(Y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm/np.sum(cm), annot=True, fmt=".2%", cmap='Blues')
plt.show()

```

Accuracy is: 90.0

2.4.2 Decision Tree Classifier

I. The Function

A Decision Tree Classifier partitions the feature space into regions and predicts the target variable based on the majority class within each region. It recursively splits the data based on feature thresholds, aiming to minimize impurity. Given input features x and classes C_k , the decision rule is:

$$\hat{y} = \operatorname{argmax}_k \sum_{i \in N(x)} I(y_i = k)$$

Where $\hat{y}$ is the predicted class, $N(x)$ is the set of samples in the region defined by x , y_i is the class of sample i and $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function.

II. Implementation

The Decision Tree Classifier is implemented as below:

```

from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
# Initialize and train the model

clf_dt = DecisionTreeClassifier(random_state=42)
clf_dt.fit(X_train, Y_train)

# Evaluate the model
y_pred = clf_dt.predict(X_test)
ac = accuracy_score(Y_test, y_pred)
print('Accuracy is: ', ac * 100)

# Generate confusion matrix and plot it
cm = confusion_matrix(Y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm/np.sum(cm), annot=True, fmt=".2%", cmap='Blues')
plt.show()

```

Accuracy is: 87.5

2.4.3 Logistic Regression Classifier

I. The Function

Logistic Regression is a binary classification algorithm used to model the probability of a categorical outcome. It utilizes the logistic function, also known as the sigmoid function, to map input features to a predicted probability of the positive class. The equation for logistic regression is:

$$P(y = 1|x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n)}}$$

Where $P(y = 1|x)$ is the probability of the positive class given input features x , β_0 is the intercept, β_i are the coefficients for each feature x_i and e is Euler's number. It optimizes these coefficients to minimize the logistic loss function, providing predictions between 0 and 1.

II. Implementation

The Logistic Regression Classifier is implemented as below:

```
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
# Initialize and train the model

clf_lg = LogisticRegression(random_state=42)
clf_lg.fit(X_train, Y_train)

# Evaluate the model
y_pred = clf_lg.predict(X_test)
ac = accuracy_score(Y_test, y_pred)
print('Accuracy is: ', ac * 100)

# Generate confusion matrix and plot it
cm = confusion_matrix(Y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm/np.sum(cm), annot=True, fmt=".2%", cmap='Blues')
plt.show()
```

Accuracy is: 85.5

2.4.4 Naïve Bayes Classifier

I. The Function

The Naive Bayes classifier is a probabilistic machine learning algorithm based on Bayes' theorem with the 'naive' assumption of independence between features. It calculates the probability of a class given input features using conditional probability. Despite its simplicity, Naive Bayes often performs well in practice and is particularly suited for text classification tasks. The equation for Naive Bayes is:

$$P(y|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{P(y) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i|y)}{P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}$$

Where $P(y|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is the probability of class y given features $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$, $P(y)$ is the prior probability of class y , and $P(x_i|y)$ is the likelihood of features x_i given class y .

II. Implementation

The Naïve Bayes Classifier is implemented as below:

```
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB

# Initialize and train the model (assuming Gaussian Naive Bayes)
clf_nb = GaussianNB()
clf_nb.fit(X_train, Y_train)

# Evaluate the model
y_pred = clf_nb.predict(X_test)
ac = accuracy_score(Y_test, y_pred)
print('Accuracy is: ', ac * 100)

# Generate confusion matrix and plot it
cm = confusion_matrix(Y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm/np.sum(cm), annot=True, fmt=".2%", cmap='Blues')
plt.show()
```

Accuracy is: 79.5

2.4.5 K-Nearest Neighbor Classifier

I. The Function

The K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN) classifier is a non-parametric method used for classification and regression tasks. It predicts the class of a sample by finding the majority class among its K nearest neighbors in the feature space. In its simplest form, Classification with K-NN involves assigning the most common class among the K

nearest neighbors. Mathematically, the prediction for a new sample x is:

$$\hat{y} = \underset{j}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{i=1}^k I(y_i=j)$$

Where $\hat{y}$ is the predicted class, y_i are the classes of the KNN, and $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function.

II. Implementation

The KNN is implemented as below:

```
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier

# Initialize and train the KNN model
clf_knn = KNeighborsClassifier()
clf_knn.fit(X_train, Y_train)

# Evaluate the model
y_pred = clf_knn.predict(X_test)
ac = accuracy_score(Y_test, y_pred)
print('Accuracy is: ', ac * 100)

# Generate confusion matrix and plot it
cm = confusion_matrix(Y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm/np.sum(cm), annot=True, fmt=".2%", cmap='Blues')
plt.show()
```

Accuracy is: 81.0

3. OBSERVATION

After applying the Machine Learning Algorithms on Breast Cancer Diagnostic dataset. We used Confusion Matrix, Accuracy, Precision, as performance metrics to evaluate and compare the models and identify the best algorithm for

breast cancer prediction. Confusion Matrix is the way to measure the performance of a classification problem where the output can be of two types of classes. A confusion matrix is a table with two dimensions viz. “Actual” and “Predicted”. Accuracy is the most common performance metric for classification algorithms. It defined the number of correct predictions made as a ratio of all predictions made. Precision, used in document retrievals, may be defined as the number of correct documents returned by our ML model.

	Predicted Class		
Actual Class		Class=Yes	Class=No
	Class=Yes	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
	Class=No	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

Table 1: Confusion Matrix

In Table 1, TP and FP are the observations that are accurately predicted and hence shown in blue shading.

Fig. 5(a): Confusion Matrix for Random Forest

Fig. 5(b): Confusion Matrix for Logistic Regression

Fig. 5(c): Confusion Matrix for Naïve Bayes

Fig. 5(d): Confusion Matrix for K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)

Fig. 5(e): Confusion Matrix for Decision Tree

For the training and validation of each model used, we worked with an adequate data set. The results are shown in Fig. 5 and Table 2. Show that the performance of each model was successful in Cancer prediction accuracy. The best performance of the proposed model is Random Forest with accuracy of 90%, while the accuracy of other models is Logistic Regression (85%), Decision Tree (87%), KNN (81%), Naïve Bayes (79%).

Algorithms	Accuracy
Random Forest	90%
Logistic Regression	85%
Decision Tree	87%
KNN	81%
Naïve Bayes	79%

Table 2: Accuracy Values

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section will present the performance of the proposed model and compare the classification algorithms used in this work based on the results of accuracy, to discover which algorithm performed better in early detection and diagnostic of breast cancer, considering that the proposed model was applied to Wisconsin Diagnostic Breast Cancer (WBDC) dataset.

The experiment of the proposed model run under Windows 10 Professional operating system, an Intel(R) Core (TM) i3-1005G1 CPU @ 1.20GHz 1.19 GHz, 4 GB of random-access memory, and 64-bit system type, with the proposed system running in a Python language environment.

In order to compare the performance of the Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classifier models, accuracy and precision measurements are used.

Fig. 6: Graphical Representation of Accuracy Comparison

Fig. 6 shows that the Random Forest gives the most accurate algorithm having classified the samples with 90% accuracy. Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, KNN and Naïve Bayes comes second, third, fourth, and fifth respectively in classification accuracy.

Fig. 7: Graphical Representation of Accuracy Comparison

Fig. 7 shows compare between classifier models based on accuracy value that present in Table 2. This compare proved that the proposed model has the ability to detection and diagnosis of malignant and benign tumors, as the proposed model was able to classify cancer with an accuracy of 90% with Random Forest.

The limitation of this analysis is that the size of the information used, the number of samples used for training and testing is low. The analysis of information with respect to the clinical settings should be administered with a bigger dataset.

5. CONCLUSION

On the Wisconsin Breast Cancer Diagnostic dataset (WBCD) we applied five main algorithms which are: Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes, and KNN, calculate, compare and evaluate different results obtained based on confusion matrix, accuracy, precision to identify the best machine learning algorithm that are precise, reliable and find the higher accuracy. All algorithms have been programmed in Python using scikit-library.

After an accurate comparison between our models, we found that Random Forest achieved a higher accuracy of 90%. In conclusion, Random Forest has demonstrated its efficiency in Breast Cancer prediction and diagnosis and achieves the best performance in terms of accuracy and precision. It should be noted that all the results obtained are related just to the WBDC database, it can be considered as a limitation of our work, it is therefore necessary to reflect for future works to apply these same algorithms and methods on other databases to confirm the results obtained via the database, as well as, in our future works, we plan to apply our and other machine learning algorithms using new parameters on larger datasets with more disease classes to obtain higher accuracy.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to acknowledge the role of **Mr. Rajesh Nag**, the guide of this paper for the guidance and freedom he has given me. I would like to further thank all the teaching staff of M.Sc. (CS) stream of Techno College Hooghly, and all the non-teaching staff of the college for providing me with the environment required to undertake this project. I would like to thank my batchmates for their regular help and support during the degree programme.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organization, "Breast cancer," 2021. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/breast-cancer> (accessed Jan. 02, 2023).
- [2] World Cancer research Fund International, "Breast cancer statistics International." <https://www.wcrf.org/cancer-trends/breast-cancerstatistics/>.

- [3] A. Sharma and P. K. Mishra, "Performance analysis of machine learning based optimized feature selection approaches for breast cancer diagnosis," *International Journal of Information Technology (Singapore)*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1949–1960, Jun. 2022, Doi: 10.1007/S41870-021-00671-5/METRICS.
- [4] Dataflow - Top 10 Data Mining Algorithms, Demystified. <https://datafloq.com/read/top-10-data-mining-algorithmsdemystified/1144>. Accessed December 29, 2015
- [5] Singh, N., & Kaur, S. (2019). A machine learning approach for breast cancer prediction. In 2019 5th International Conference on Advanced Computing & Communication Systems (ICACCS) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [6] OMS, "Breast cancer." <https://www.who.int/es/news-room/factsheets/detail/breast-cancer> (accessed Jan. 02, 2023).
- [7] H. Y. Tsai et al., "Integration of Clinical and CT-Based Radiomic Features for Pretreatment Prediction of Pathologic Complete Response to Neoadjuvant Systemic Therapy in Breast Cancer," *Cancers (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 24, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.3390/CANCERS14246261
- [8] K. N. Chitrala, M. Nagarkatti, P. Nagarkatti, and S. Yeguvapalli, "Analysis of the TP53 deleterious single nucleotide polymorphisms impact on estrogen receptor alpha-p53 interaction: A machine learning approach," *Int J Mol Sci*, vol. 20, no. 12, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.3390/IJMS20122962.